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**THE FIRST WORLD
WAR ON THE WEB -
THE CASE OF SERBIA**

FIRST WORLD WAR CENTENARY

- numerous projects on the WWI have been initiated and implemented worldwide, by using new technologies and media, with a goal:
 - to connect experts from various fields
 - to facilitate the access to historical sources and archival material
 - to present results of researches
 - to organize virtual exhibitions
 - to advance teaching process and education

GOAL OF THE PAPER

- to study phenomena on using new technologies in historical science based on analysis of form, structure and content of several most representative Web presentations
- to study the development in perception of historical sources, archival material and the representation of the results of the scientific researches
 - **example of Serbia and Serbian cyber space**

International Encyclopedia of the First World War

- made as a result of a common project of more than a thousand experts from more than fifty countries

Prisoners of the First World War

- International Committee of the Red Cross Historical Archives - 5 M indexed cards / 2 M prisoners

The screenshot displays the ICRC website interface for the '1914-1918 PRISONERS OF THE FIRST WORLD WAR ICRC HISTORICAL ARCHIVES'. The page features a navigation menu with options like 'SEARCH FOR A PERSON', 'EXAMPLES OF INDEX CARDS', 'LIFE IN INTERNMENT CAMPS', and 'DIGITISATION - BEHIND THE SCENE'. Below the menu, there is a section titled 'List of the camps' which includes a 'NEARBY:' filter set to 'All' and a list of camp names such as AFYONKARAHISAR, ALBITA, ALERIA, ALESSANDRIA, ALGER, PONT-DE-BOUGIE, AMBERG, ANDREZIEUX-BOUTHEON, AERODROME, ASCHAFFENBURG, ASPERG, ASTI, ATHENS, ATHENS, PIRAEUS, ATZENDORF, MINE, and AUGSBOURG. The main content is a map of Europe with numerous numbered markers (1-15) indicating the locations of camps across various countries including the United Kingdom, France, Germany, Poland, Italy, Spain, Greece, Turkey, Romania, and Ukraine. The map also shows major cities and geographical features.

Europeana 1914-1918 – untold stories & official histories of WW1

- Europeana 1914-1918 mixes resources from libraries and archives across the globe with memories and memorabilia from families throughout Europe

Europeana 1914-1918

Home Add your story Browse

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Europeana 1914-1918 – untold stories & official histories of WW1

Explore stories, films and historical material about the First World War and contribute your own family history. Europeana 1914-1918 mixes resources from libraries and archives across the globe with memories and memorabilia from families throughout Europe. Discover. Learn. Research. Use. Share.

Search

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Upcoming Events

Latvia

Riga
Community Collection Days
NEW DATES: Sunday 6 & Monday 7 November 2016
National Library, Riga
Details will follow soon

News

The Battle of the Somme

On the occasion of the Battle of the Somme Centenary we would like to point at some of the rich and varied stories and imagery that can be found on our website. Please click on the short presentation below if you like to know more.

Commemorating

11:07 PM 9/27/2016

Österreichisches Staatsarchiv, 1914-2014 - 100 Jahre erster Weltkrieg

100 Jahre erster Weltkrieg x

← → ↻ wk1.staatsarchiv.at

1914-2014
100 JAHRE ERSTER WELTKRIEG

ÖSTERREICHISCHES STAATSARCHIV

NAVIGATION

f t g+

KRIEGSEUPHORIE

KRIEGSFINANZIERUNG

KRIEGSFOTOGRAFIE

DER KRIEG UND DER ADEL

DIPLOMATIE ZWISCHEN KRIEG UND FRIEDEN

FRAU IM KRIEG

ZEITLEISTE

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STARTSEITE, KONTAKT, QUELLENVERZEICHNIS, IMPRESSUM, PROJEKTEAM

11:16 PM
9/27/2016

Digital projects around the First World War

- individual historians' presentation:
Otto Vervaart' blog

The screenshot displays the 'digital 1418' WordPress blog. The browser address bar shows the URL <https://digital1418.wordpress.com/about/>. The page features a dark blue header with navigation links: HOME, ABOUT, SUBJECTS, and FINDING MORE. A search bar is located in the top right corner of the header. The main content area is titled 'ABOUT' and contains the following text:

This blog started in February 2014 as a simple initiative to use the powers of the system behind it as a kind of ready-made database to enhance searching for relevant digital projects concerning the First World War. For each project on this website I create a post with a concise description enriched with tags and categories. By clicking on tags – at the right – or categories – at the left – or by using the search function you can find particular projects. Projects can fall into several categories and have one or more tags, and thus I try to escape from too narrow classifications, definitions and descriptions. Presenting projects from many countries helps also to view the First World War from different and less obvious perspectives. I try to avoid focusing solely on websites accessible in English or on developments in Western Europe. It is impossible to reach complete coverage of all possible subjects, and thus you can find here also information about portals guiding you for [further research](#).

The inspiration for this blog comes from [A Compendium of Digital Collections](#), a pioneer website now no longer updated of the [University of New Hampshire](#) created with a blogging system. The concept is perfectly suitable when you restrict its realization to just

On the right side of the page, there is a 'SEARCH...' section with a search input field. Below it is a 'RECENT POSTS' section listing several articles:

- Fairbank Papers
- Jutland 1916
- The Battle of Jutland Centenary Initiative
- Lester S. Levy Sheet Music Collection
- Grand Mémorial
- Lions led by donkeys
- La Grande Collecte
- Letters of 1916: A Year in the Life
- Nieuws van de Groote Oorlog
- First World War Volunteers British Red Cross

The left sidebar contains a 'digital 1418' logo and a description: 'Digital projects around the First World War'. It also lists 'CATEGORIES' (Archives, Armies, Exhibitions, Libraries, Lieux de mémoire, Museums, Portals, Sources, Study centers) and 'BLOGROLL' (1914-1818: Ein rheinisches Tagebuch - Quellen aus Archiven des Rheinlands, 1914: Mitten in Europa - Das Rheinland und der Erste Weltkrieg, Africa and the First World War, BCU 1914-1918 - Bibliothèque Clermont Université, Genre et Guerre - Gender and

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the system clock as 11:41 PM on 9/27/2016.

- this material today easily accessible for the users from all around the world illustrates in the correct way changes and challenges modern generations of historians are faced with
- it introduces numerous heuristic possibilities
- series of methodological problems and questions about use of information and historical sources taken from the Internet
 - ✦ partial digitalization of fonds and collections
 - ✦ fetishism of the documents, often without any selection in reconstructing of the past

Example of Serbia and Serbian Syber Space

- public interest for this topic is huge: numerous publications relating to the WWI have been published in Serbia in the past few years, many exhibitions, conferences, public manifestations and television shows have been organized and recorded
- only several Web presentation have been released, which allowed full perception of the historical events that are of great importance in the collective memory
- several important projects have been realized significantly enriching the possibilities of researches, studies and work in digital environment

Historical Archives of Belgrade

- Project First World War in Fonds and Collections of The Historical Archives of Belgrade – Online Digital Thematic Guide

FIRST WORLD GREAT WAR

Home About Timeline **Guide** Articles Bibliography Impresum Links Contact

FIRST WORLD WAR IN FONDS AND COLLECTIONS OF THE HISTORICAL ARCHIVES OF BELGRADE

The period of the Great War was studied in Serbian historiography considerably and a great number of sources and papers have been published, mostly analyzing political and military events. Data about Belgrade in this period are less available. This can be partly justified by the fact that in October 1915 a great number of citizens and government officials had left Serbian capital taking away entire documentation of government institutions. It is the reason why documentation about First World War preserved in Historical Archives of Belgrade is fragmented, especially documentation from two most important city institutions: Belgrade City Administration and Municipality of Belgrade.

Thematic guide, as scientific informative aid, whose goal is to inform and direct researcher to thematically specific material, was created in 2014 and it represents a result of a long research of one group of archivists.

Data from archival material are classified according to groups of fonds and collections, in accordance to the Review of archival fonds and collections of Association of Societies of archivists of Yugoslavia (1978). A short introduction is offered for each fonds and collection, with basic information about preserved material from WWI, and then analytical descriptions of individual documents follow. Documents are classified according to the structure of fonds and collections. Besides analytical processing of all important documents from archival material, a selection from library collection is analytically processed as well. Articles and photographs from *Ilustrovani list* (Illustrated magazine) from 1920 and 1921 are analytically processed, since they represent significant addition to selected archival material.

Archival material in the Thematic guide represents primary historical source for the researchers and it can reconstruct complete picture of life in occupied Belgrade in the period from 1914 to 1918.

Highlights...

GALLERY

Database (Testament of King Petar I Karađorđević)

188.120.97.145:81/docman/projekti/ww1/ww1_popis.cfm?startrow=594&mPolje=0&mTrazi=princip&scr_height=945&flag_last_id=0&m_fond=0:&m_filter2=0&m_filter3=0&m_filter4=0 conclusion

Arhivistika Browse History Comp_Hist fotografija guitar Mediji razno INFO muzika UDI HIT! film Privremeno racunari XX Vek Harp Most Visited Getting Started

Istorijski Arhiv Beograda - Sektor za obradu i korišćenje arhivske građe
Slobodan Mandić - slobodan

SPOLJNI PROJEKTI
PRVI SVETSKI RAT U FONDovima ARHIVA BEOGRADA

ГЛАВНИ МЕНИ Избор фонда: НОВИ УНОС ПРЕТРАГА

ИЗМЕНА ПОСТОЈЕЋЕГ ЗАПИСА

НАЗИВ ИЗ ЈАНУС-а	НАЗИВ - КОНВЕРЗИЈА У ЛАТИНИЦУ
Тестамент краља Петра I	Testament kralja Petra I
САДРЖАЈ ИЗ ЈАНУС-а	САДРЖАЈ - КОНВЕРЗИЈА У ЛАТИНИЦУ
Тестамент краља Петра I, писан пред полазак у рат 18. новембра 1914. године, којим је оставио папире и новац својој деци, Александру, Ђорђу и Јелени, имање и земљишту у Београду наследнику престола Александру као и цркву на Опленцу која постаје засебна установа под именом "Задужбина Краља Петра". Болница у Тополи предаје се држави на употребу. У тестаменту је додаток према коме оставља Здравку, свом момку, пет хиљада динара. Тестамент је објављен 22. септембра 1922. године. ИАБ, ЗАрх, К 7/ПФ К, 9	Testament kralja Petra I, pisan pred polazak u rat 18. novembra 1914. godine, kojim je ostavio papire i novac svojoj deci, Aleksandru, Đorđu i Jeleni, imanje i zemljištu u Beogradu nasledniku prestola Aleksandru kao i crkvu na Oplencu koja postaje zasebna ustanova pod imenom "Zadužbina Kralja Petra". Bolnica u Topoli predaje se državi na upotrebu. U testamentu je dodatak prema kome ostavlja Zdravku, svom momku, pet hiljada dinara. Testament je objavljen 22. septembra 1922. godine. IAB, ZArh, K 7/PF K, 9
НАЗИВ - ПРЕВОД НА ЕНГЛЕСКИ	
Testament of King Petar I Karađorđević	
САДРЖАЈ - ПРЕВОД НА ЕНГЛЕСКИ	
Testament of King Petar I Karađorđević, written before he had left to war on November 18th 1914; he left in the testament all documentation and money to his children Aleksandar, Đorđe and Jelena, property and land in Belgrade to the heir of the throne Aleksandar, as well as church on Oplenac, which would remain as a separate institution named "Endowment of King Petar". The hospital in Topola he left to the state. In the addition to the testament he left 5 000 dinars for his "boy" Zdravko. The testament was made public on September 22nd 1922. IAB, ZArh, K 7/PF K, 9	

МЕТАПОДАЦИ

Подаци из ЈАНУС-а	Индекси
Р.Б. у водичу: 589	Тематски индекс (подтеме) Бољесни и рањени X Династија Карађорђевић X Финансије / Банке X Црква / свештенство X <input type="checkbox"/> Закључај
Фонд: ЗБИРКА АРХИВАЛИЈА	Именски индекс Александар Карађорђевић X Карађорђевић Ђорђе X Карађорђевић Јелена X Петар I Карађорђевић X
Сигнатура: К7/ПФ К, 9	Временска координата: 19141118
Настанак: Крагујевац, 18. новембар 1914.	Географска коорд.: Крагујевац
Количина: оригинал, л. 7	ПОТВРДИ
Језик: српски	
Дигитална копија: 01187-00589 ОТВОРИ	

Објава Штаба Врховне команде у Скадру Димитрију Стојановићу, пешајском поручнику, о одобреном боловању у иностранству ИАБ, ЗАрх. К7/ПФ П-Ц.32

12:38 AM 9/28/2016

presentations focusing on a specific chronological and geographical point

Web 2.0 tools

CONCLUSION

- basic characteristics/problem - cooperation of different experts / interdisciplinary approach
- good material for retrospection of relations between historical science and challenges of new technologies' implementation today and in the future
- the necessity to reconstruct historical science for digital era
- to introduce more complex attitude towards social reality
- small number of reviews and critiques in the field of digital history
- larger interpretation and implementation of results of already finalized projects
- to motivate and involve wider audience in the field of digital history

THANK YOU

**FOR YOUR
ATTENTION!**